

ReNEW

Capacity Building and Policy
Recommendations v1

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Acronyms and Abbreviations	Meaning
ALICE	Alliance for Logistics Innovations through Collaboration
APA	Portuguese Environment Agency
APDL	Administration Porto De Leixoes
DGRM	Directorate-General for Natural Resources, Safety and Maritime Services
DT	Digital Twins
ETP	European Technology Platform
EU	European Union
FMP	Floating Modular Platforms
GA	Grant Agreement
IoT	Internet of Things
IWT	Inland Waterways Transport
Mx	Month x
ReNEW	Resilience-centric smart, green, Networked EU Inland Waterways
RIS	River information services
WP	Work Package
ZEWT	Zero-emission waterborne transport

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Executive summary

This document represents the initial version of a deliverable that aims to develop a capacity building strategy and formulate policy recommendations in the form of a white paper. This deliverable is linked to Task 5.4, which started in M12 of the project and will continue until the M36, which is also the deadline for the final version of this deliverable.

The focus of this version will be on the context of the inland waterway system and the project itself. It will also describe the information that is still missing and the methodology that can be used to gather this information. Finally, it will explain how the gathered information will be utilised to create the capacity building strategy and the policy recommendations in the final version of the deliverable at the end of the project.

The capacity building strategy is defined as a guide to help organisations overcome barriers to the implementation of new technologies, specifically those studied within the project. Legislative barriers will be given extra attention in the form of policy recommendations. Both the capacity building progress and the policy recommendations are crucial for organizations in the inland waterway system to be able to implement innovations and improve their processes.

The introduction will emphasise the importance of the project and the need for capacity building and policy recommendations. The second chapter will describe the diversity of stakeholders involved in the project, especially within the living labs, and outline the objectives of the use cases. The third chapter will summarise the stakeholder mapping and explain how additional information will be gathered through interviews and surveys to understand the differences between stakeholder groups. This information will inform the capacity building strategy, taking into account the specific needs of each group. The final version of the deliverable will present the capacity building strategy and policy recommendations developed based on the gathered information and input from other parts of the project.

1 Introduction

1.1 Overview of the project

The resilience of the Inland waterways transport (IWT) system depends on the reliability of the infrastructure and the IWT fleet. Furthermore, due to the increasing dynamics, heterogeneity and complexity of inland waterway systems, it is becoming more and more difficult for the system to cope with serious predictable and, in particular, unexpected events.

The digitalisation of the transport sector is seen by the European Commission as a key enabler for smart solutions that can support the resilience and sustainability of IWT and deliver economic, environmental and societal benefits. Industrial data spaces, simulation and digital twins (DTs) have gained importance in recent years in various fields (e.g. Industry 4.0, smart manufacturing, intelligent transport and smart cities). Simulation and DTs are used to predict outcomes and evaluate what-if scenarios. This leads to better real-time optimisation of processes and operations. Thus, DTs can be a decision support system for industry to achieve resilience and system decarbonisation based on cross-domain modelling standards and innovative architectures.

Furthermore, it is important to have the right infrastructure that can flexibly handle unexpected events and provide a link between IWT and other transport modes, so that proposed solutions resulting from simulations and DT can be effectively implemented.

The ReNEW (Resilience-centric smart, green, Networked EU Inland Waterways) project aims to study and demonstrate how this digitalisation of the IWT sector and the current or new infrastructure (including vessels) could go hand in hand. The aim is to make the sector a smarter, greener, more sustainable and climate resilient sector.

After studying and demonstrating various innovations, the question will arise as to how the sector will be able to implement these innovations. This brings us to the purpose and scope of this deliverable, capacity building and policy recommendations.

1.2 Purpose and Scope of the Capacity Building and policy recommendation deliverable

Firstly, it is important to note that this deliverable is the first version of a two-version deliverable with the final version to be delivered in month 36, at the end of this project. The focus of this document is on the context of the inland waterway system and what information is needed to complete this context. A thorough description of the context will provide the basis for developing a capacity building strategy and formulating policy recommendations.

Why is capacity building important? It describes how different organisations, in this case organisations that are part of the inland waterway system, will be able to implement innovations in

their own processes, in particular those that are demonstrated within the ReNEW project. It provides guidance on what improvements are needed within the organisations. This can be both physical (e.g. infrastructure) and knowledge-based (e.g. employee skills and know-how). The aim is to enable businesses to implement innovations with a lasting, sustainable impact. Where there are regulatory barriers for enterprises, these will be addressed through policy recommendations to the EU Commission.

In order to formulate a capacity building strategy, it is necessary to know the context of this project and also the context in which the IWT systems exist. How the IWT system interacts with the rest of the world, what impacts it could have and what impacts it is having. This starts with a description of the partners involved in the projects and the innovations demonstrated in the four Living Labs. The interaction between the IWT system and the rest of the world is described in terms of challenges and opportunities, followed by an assessment of the IWT system itself. The aim is to describe which characteristics of the IWT system make it unique and what specific barriers result from this for the uptake of innovations. The first information will be the stakeholders, which will be analysed and mapped. This part will be done under D5.1&2 "Communication and Dissemination Plan". This will give insights into the different categories of companies within the IWT system and learn about their specificities that require a different approach. An example of this is the difference between barge companies and a single vessel company, which do not have the same financial resources.

The next step will be to assess the IWT system and its ability to adapt to new technologies. This will also take into account the differences between the categories of companies. A number of areas will be assessed, the first of which will be related to the strengths and weaknesses at company level within the IWT system. This will include: skills and knowledge gaps, internal organisation, operational gaps, etc. The second part will be an assessment of the IWT system that is common to all parts of the IWT system: IWT infrastructure, policies, financial resources for innovation... The chapter will end with the different methods that can be used to collect this information.

By bringing together both the context and the assessment of the IWT system, this information can be used for capacity building and policy recommendations. Using the information and experiences from the different Living Labs, best practices and strategies on how to overcome certain barriers will be formulated. Policy gaps will also be identified, and possible solutions will be formulated as policy recommendations at the end of the project.

1.3 Mapping the ReNEW Output

The following Table 1-1 maps the ReNEW’s Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work to perform.

Table 1-1: Adherence to ReNEW’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

Deliverable D5.8 Capacity Building and Policy Recommendations v1		
<p>Report collating initial capacity building progress. This report will describe the importance of capacity building and policy recommendations. Further it will also describe the strategy to formulate the final capacity building strategy and the policy recommendations in the final version of the deliverable 5.9 due date month 36.</p>		
Task T5.4 Capacity Building and Policy Recommendations		
<p>To support the impact of ReNEW Capacity Building and Policy Recommendations, a survey exploring the response of a wide group of categorised stakeholders to proposed solutions, fields of application, rate of implementation, acceptance and support, incorporation of resilience strategies in company and governmental strategies, perceived roles for various stakeholders including government, etc., will be conducted to provide guidelines and focus points for the upscaling-capacity building and explore gaps to maximise efficient policy recommendations. The results will be also shared with logistics clusters in Europe connected to the ALICE network for additional input and uptake in the respective logistics clusters’ networks</p>		
ReNEW GA Element Title	ReNEW GA Element Outline	Respective Document Chapter (s) and Description
ST5.4.1 Upscaling Capacity Building	Two symposia will be scheduled (M24, M28) with the goal to incentivise for the accelerated adoption of ReNEW initiatives, innovation blueprints, the methodology and the open tooling on IWT. The capacity building aims to integrate ReNEW as courses related to resilience and reliability increase in the view of climate crisis to Inland Waterways, the use of Simulation Models in creating and assessing risk scenarios, and the novel reconfigurable resources deployment	In both chapter 3.1 and 3.2 it is described which context elements are needed to create a capacity building strategy plan that has specifics for each different stakeholder group. The two symposia’s will be used for dissemination of the learnings of the project and gathering more information on potential barriers for implementation and upscaling.

	<p>as well as the multimodal alternatives networks to mitigate disasters. Training for Transferability will provide a course for different user profiles and lecture material collaboratively produced, aligned with parallel actions and projects and led by ReNEW research and academic participants.</p>	
<p>ST5.4.2</p>	<p>The Policy recommendations will be based on policy assessment for responses to hazardous situations in Inland Waterways caused by natural or human caused disasters, and the societal impacts of the ReNEW initiatives and the innovations introduced as the autonomous barges (WP2) that will lead to reorganisation of Human Resources, fostering policy making interactions with the project stakeholders in the view of the project results. The main outputs will be white papers and a roadmap of actions and a set of key policy recommendations and best practices and social impacts with the aim of maximising the impact of ReNEW, in support of relevant EC strategies.</p>	<p>In chapter 3.1 is described how the current policies will be mapped with the help of research and experience from the living labs. In chapter 3.2 is outlined how the current policies are evaluated and if they create any barriers. Policy recommendations will be propose to overcome these barriers.</p>

2 Context and background

2.1 Involved Partners

In the ReNEW deliverable D5.1 "Communication and Dissemination Plan", PNO has defined a tailor-made value chain (Figure 2-1) to represent the various activities carried out by the project partners to promote the decarbonisation of IWT and to improve the sustainability and resilience of the sector. This value chain encompasses all potential actions and entities involved in this process, divided into two blocks: one focused on providers of resilient solutions for IWT, and the other related to the infrastructures that will adopt these developed solutions.

The two value chain blocks comprise three main segments: **Green and Resilient IWT Software Developers, Systems Engineering and Integration**, and **Infrastructure Management**. Each segment is further subdivided into sub-categories. Software developers include digital twin developers, traffic/navigation management units, IoT/connectivity innovators and autonomy facilitators. Systems engineering and integration includes ship and pontoon designers, shipyards, remote control centres, infrastructure systems engineering and power supply providers. Infrastructure management includes fixed and mobile operators and managers. In addition, there are horizontal stakeholders such as investors/financiers, policy makers and regulators, industry associations, classification and insurance companies and various other service providers. These have significant influence on the entire value chain and contribute to the improvement of greener and more resilient IWT within the ReNEW project. Further details and descriptions can be found in D5.1.

Figure 2-1: ReNEW Value chain, project partners

The representation of the value chain within the ReNEW project highlights critical stakeholders, but notably lacks the involvement of policy makers, fleet/cargo management companies and shippers. These entities play central roles within the IWT sector. Policy makers, who are instrumental in regulating and shaping the sector, have significant influence. Similarly, fleet/cargo management companies and shippers, who are responsible for managing cargo operations and transport, are integral parts of the value chain. Their involvement would strengthen and enrich the broad landscape of stakeholders involved in advancing the ReNEW project's objectives for a greener and more resilient IWT.

As a next step, PNO has asked all Living Lab Manager partners to provide data on current subcontractors and engaged stakeholders within the project. This is described per Living Lab below.

2.1.1 Living Lab 1: Ghent's Multifunctional Synchro-modality City Logistics Hub

Within this living lab there are 4 use cases that will be described separately.

Use Case 1: Smart terminal

Objective: The design and the construction of a resilient Smart Terminal (connected with water, road and rail) and the ability to deploy the resilience-assist modular platform and pontoons when appropriate. Furthermore, provide a mobile command centre (backed up with a Shore Control Centre in Antwerp and Rotterdam) for managing the vessels with smart navigation, an automated mooring system and loading/unloading activities of the ships. Further the goal is to be able to manage all data from ships, the shore and the control centre, within dataspace and with the use of a Digital Twin. The Digital Twin will also be used as an interface for analysing the gathered data and also for the prediction and scenario models.

Stakeholders: The main stakeholders will be the partners involved within the specific task and mainly OHB who will design the modular platforms and pontoons and Seafar in lead of the control centre. If there are specific needs OHB will look for other partners to cooperate with.

Use Case 2: Floating Modular Platforms (FMP)

Objective: Produce solutions for resilience and sustainability, in the form of FMPs. This will be achieved by creating resilience-assist modular platform as "emergency transport and urban battery". Within this use case it is the goal to implement floating platforms with superior manoeuvrability, platooning capability and movable emergency power supply capabilities enabling stationary position even in high streams. Lastly a new automated mooring system at the quay of the infrastructure will be developed and installed. This makes the ships able to autonomously moor under the loading system, and to test automated loading/unloading of cargo.

Stakeholders: Mainly OHB who will lead the design with the help of the other technical partners within the consortium.

Use Case 3: Environmental alert system

Objective: By installing sensors onboard ships more information about the rivers and regions near the rivers can be gathered. Examples of this information are: water level, air pollution, CO₂, NO_x, particulate matter, etc. This information can be used to measure ongoing disruption or even help to predict them. This information will be collected and analysed by a mobile control centre and saved within the cloud. This mobile centre can also be connected to government alert institutions, through the cloud, to be able to notify about possible upcoming disruption or monitoring disruption as they occur.

Stakeholders: Main stakeholders are the partners involved within this task and also the governmental institutes that monitor disruption.

Use Case 4: Emergency supply chain

Objective: Use of the “floating power supply” vessel in connection with the other vessels as giant power supply in cascade effect. The idea is that when one battery is almost empty it can sail away to get connected to the off-grid power supply as Solar park, windmills, etc.

Stakeholders: Main stakeholders are the partners involved with this task, the possible business case should be checked with possible users.

2.1.2 Living Lab 2: Smart Douro Inland Waterway management

This Living lab is divided in 2 uses cases.

Use Case 1: Illegal Waste Water dumping

Objective: The main objective is to create a digital twin of the hydrological behaviour of the Douro River. This twin will serve as a tool to support decision making during extreme weather events such as floods and droughts. The focus will be on improving the accuracy of predictions, adapting responses to different scenarios and taking into account critical factors such as existing rail connections, especially their role in emergency situations such as evacuation of passengers and goods.

Stakeholders: The main stakeholders are the partners directly involved in the specific task of the project. In particular, APDL has been instrumental in providing essential data, an issue highlighted in recent General Assembly discussions.

Use Case 2: Extreme conditions

Objective: This case emphasises the promotion of respect for the environment in the Douro River, with a particular focus on water quality. The objective is to implement a continuous monitoring of wastewater deposits from ships, in order to prevent illegal dumping. The identification of the blockchain solution provider is pending the completion of the cost analysis, as well as the selection of specific operators involved in the wastewater management pilots.

Stakeholders: Entities such as the Portuguese Environment Agency (APA) and the Directorate-General for Natural Resources, Safety, and Maritime Services (DGRM) play pivotal roles. Their involvement is crucial in refining requirements, discussing legal and operational implications, managing the legislative process, and accepting the means of verifying non-compliance. Unlike APDL, the APA and DGRM are responsible for controlling the quality of the Douro's water. Therefore, APDL,

as the managing authority and infrastructure provider, needs their agreement and cooperation for the successful implementation of the pilot project.

Operators of the Douro: Meetings were held to gauge interest in participating in the pilot. Factors relevant to future use, such as incentives for collaborating companies, improved trip planning and avoiding undue advantage for non-compliant operators, were discussed.

Technological Partners: Meetings have been held to explain the project and analyse how the outputs and data generated by the devices can be managed. These discussions focus on the seamless integration of the selected blockchain-based technological solution for the implementation of the pilot.

2.1.3 Living Lab 3: Planning mitigation demonstrator app for climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, and in addition to boost modal shift

Objective: The development in LL3 will address the specific situation on the East and South Corridor in The Netherlands. The goal is to add a planning and mitigation module to an existing routing tool. Through this tool users can do the planning of their inland waterway transport and make them able to act in real-time on disruptions. This is made possible by seamless integration of planning services with real-time information about disruptions. The system will provide a sophisticated mitigation strategies by an advice algorithm. This algorithm is based on data of all disruptions from the last years and all mitigation strategies adopted. This creates a knowledge base of problems connected to solutions that were adopted in certain conditions and in certain locations.

Stakeholders: The main stakeholders are the partners directly involved in the specific task of the project.

2.1.4 Living Lab 4: Resilience promoting Autonomous zero-emissions barges

Objective: the focus of this living lab is strengthening the resilience of autonomous zero-emission barges, secure the active involvement of key stakeholders currently in the potential collaboration phase.

Stakeholders: Danser, identified as a potential customer, is expected to provide valuable insight into the requirements of the project. Vard Electro, positioned as a potential technical supplier, is expected to bring expertise in the development of autonomous systems. The shipyard and the autonomous system provider, yet to be determined, are key entities expected to play a pivotal role in the implementation of the project. Regulatory stakeholders, including De Vlaamse Waterweg (Flanders),

Centrale Commissie voor de Rijnvaart, Rijkswaterstaat (The Netherlands), and Wasserstraßen- und Schifffahrtsverwaltung des Bundes (Germany), will ensure compliance with inland waterway regulations. Citymesh will be considered for communication needs, while ZENOBE or ZES are potential energy providers. Mooring systems and the specific shipyard are yet to be determined. In particular, key ports such as Duisburg, North Sea ports, and Nijmegen BCTN are also potential participants. The collaboration with ZULU and Sintef Ocean, as outlined in the ReNEW project, underlines the importance of these potential partnerships in achieving the goals of the Living Lab.

2.2 Current Challenges and Opportunities

This chapter will describe a selection of the current challenges and opportunities which are studied within this project, this will be further completed within the next version of this deliverable. For the challenges that have to do with how IWT is organised, the IWT sector within Germany is taken as an example.

2.2.1 Challenges

Composition of the IWT sector

The IWT market is made up of small enterprises; in fact, it is dominated by micro-enterprises with less than 10 employees, often owning barges and being a family business [11]. In the Netherlands, for example, a large proportion of the companies are independent enterprises with only two crew members on each vessel, which limits them to daytime or semi-continuous operations and is most prevalent in the transport of dry goods. About 90% of the companies have only one vessel and only 5% have more than two vessels. Multi-vessel ownership is more common in the more specialised types of transport (tankers, containers, tugs and passenger transport).

Labour shortage – unfavourable conditions to work in the IWT sector

Crew members can be divided into two groups: self-employed and mobile workers. Self-employed members can be described as owner-operators, whether or not they are registered as employees for social security purposes, or as crew members and other on-board personnel who are self-employed according to national definitions. Mobile workers are defined as any worker employed as a member of the travelling crew of an undertaking engaged in the transport of passengers or goods by inland waterway. The situation of mobile workers is unfavourable for workers due to insecure contracts, low wages and no or very short rest periods.

IWT infrastructure

There is a certain scarcity of transshipment infrastructure, especially inland multimodal terminals, which requires a higher efficiency of the inland waterway system. Other drawbacks include the restriction to follow the waterways (compared to road transport, for which the network is much more extensive). This will require significant investment in IWT and multimodal infrastructure, fleet

modernisation and digitalisation, as well as adjustments to the EU policy and regulatory framework. [8] The economic downturn, combined with fierce price competition from other modes of transport, has discouraged investment in new or innovative technologies and has resulted in the majority of vessels being old and ill-equipped for the planned transition to zero-emission mobility [9].

IWT policies and organisation structure differs per country: Example Germany

In **Germany**, the inland shipping is categorized based on waterways (e.g., Rhine navigation, Danube navigation) and operational forms (private, company, and industrial shipping).

Corporate Structure

A characteristic feature of inland shipping in the Federal Republic of Germany is the coexistence of shipping companies (entities with their own onshore organisation for the acquisition and disposition of freight; conducting commercial transport with their own or third-party cargo space), a multitude of private shipowners (independent ship owners with a maximum of three vessels and without their own onshore freight handling organization), and industrial and commercial enterprises engaged in so-called industrial transportation. The latter, however, are losing significance because there are changes - deregulations - in the legal framework conditions ("Güterkraftverkehrsgesetz = Road freight transport act") for own-account transport that affect the activities of these companies.

Types of Vessels and Their Carrying Capacity

In Western Europe, the main inland waterway transport modes are self-propelled barges, pusher barges and coupled barges. Self-propelled barges typically have a deadweight capacity of 300-4,500 tonnes and are suitable for the transport of bulk and liquid goods, and increasingly for the transport of containers, breakbulk and plant components. Pushed convoys typically consist of four (or six on some waterways, such as the Lower Rhine) box-shaped unmanned barges coupled side by side and pushed by a rigidly connected pusher (the deadweight of standard barges varies between 1,250 and 2,800 tonnes). Coupled convoys consist of a motor cargo vessel equipped for pushing and up to three barges. In addition, specialised vessels (container carriers, lash barges, ro-ro vessels, tankers, gas carriers, etc.) are increasingly used in Germany's IWT.

Challenges: As inland shipping is traditionally suited to the transport of bulk goods, the quantitative decline in orders from the coal and steel industries also affects inland shipping. The volume transported in these commodity classes is decreasing. The increasing substitution of petroleum products, especially heating oil, is also leading to a loss of transport volume for IWT, which is currently looking for new products to fill the resulting demand gap. In response, IWT is increasingly focusing on container and ro-ro transport, but these modes can only partially compensate for the losses in bulk transport. German IWT faces the challenge of strong competitive pressure, especially from the Dutch fleet. Past national and

supranational scrapping initiatives have not solved the problem of overcapacity, so that a further decline in German IWT is not unlikely if new routes cannot be sufficiently developed. Even the good capacity utilisation and operating results of recent years cannot hide this problem.

2.2.2 Opportunities

Sustainable transport mode

IWT has some significant advantages over other modes of transport, especially for certain types of goods such as bulk goods, dangerous goods and oversized goods. It contributes to one of the main challenges for transport policy makers, namely the reduction of negative environmental externalities, by improving the sustainability performance of the transport network. For example, the transport of goods by inland waterways uses only about 17% of the energy per tonne-kilometre of road transport and 50% of that of rail transport, and also produces significantly less noise [1], so there are clear opportunities for the sector to develop and increase its modal share. This is also reflected in the modal shift strategy of the EU and its Member States, as expressed in:

- The European Green Deal [2], which says that a substantial part of the 75% of inland freight carried today by road should shift onto rail and inland waterways.
- The Sustainable and Smart mobility strategy, in particular point 45 “Transport by inland waterways and short sea shipping will increase by 25% by 2030 and by 50% by 2050” [3].
- The Zero Pollution Action Plan [4] with its objectives towards zero pollution.
- The IWT sector’s modal share can be further increased and river information services (RIS) is expected to contribute to that effort. [10]

A side note here is that IWT could also have a negative impact on the environment, like habitat disruption or water pollution.

Safety

Safety is another crucial advantage of IWT, especially for the transport of dangerous goods, compared to other possible options [5]. Furthermore, IWT can play an important role in coping with the continuing growth of transport, as it has large capacities to offer [6]. The fact that 75% of EU waterway transport crosses borders underlines the importance of measures to harmonise the exchange of information and to support the overall interoperability of systems along Europe's inland waterways [7].

3 Strategy

This chapter will describe what the further steps are in the second half of the project towards the formulation of the capacity building strategy and the policy recommendations. The separate theme's that will be further analysed and the methods that will be used will be discussed in the capacity assessment part. In the second part the context and the further analysis will formulate the capacity building strategy and the policy recommendations.

The capacity assessment will include the analysis of the stakeholders, the assessment of the IWT-system and the adaptability capabilities. The stakeholder analysis will map actors that are involved in the IWT-system in the same way it was done with the own consortium members. This part was done by PNO in the ReNEW deliverable D5.1, for completeness a summary of the first analysis will be added within this deliverable and updated in the final one.

The IWT system assessment will focus on the weaknesses and strengths of the IWT system as a whole. It will use what is listed in 2.2 and will focus on the differences between different categories of stakeholders within the IWT- system, this will also include the listing of important policies. In the assessment of the adaptability the effect of these strengths and weaknesses on the implementation of newly innovations by these stakeholders will be assessed. The chapter will finish with the different methods and sources that will be used to gather extra input for the final version of this deliverable.

Finally, it will be described how all this will be used to formulate the capacity building strategy and policy recommendations in the final version of this deliverable at the end of the project.

3.1 Capacity assessment

Within the ReNEW project the IWT-system itself will be researched in other work packages of the project. This research in combination with the several use cases within the different living labs will be used as source for the assessment of the IWT-system. This will be used as a valuable input for the capacity building and policy recommendations. The part that is most important for the specific task coupled to this deliverable will be the specific barriers that companies or organisations encounter for implementing the newly studied innovations within this project.

3.1.1 Stakeholder Analysis and Mapping

During the initial stages of the ReNEW project, a stakeholder analysis was conducted as part of the **D5.1 'Communication and Dissemination Plan'** using PNO's innovative tool, [WheesBee](#). This analysis aimed to align with the core objectives of ReNEW, focusing on building a robust innovation ecosystem. To achieve this, there were selected **131 European-funded projects**, initiated from

01/01/2014 onwards. The selection is guided by the projects mentioned in the proposal in which ReNEW partners have participated.

Figure 3-1 ReNEW potential stakeholders, source: ReNEW D5.1

The subsequent stage involved analysing and describing the participant organisations in the selected projects to position them in the ReNEW project's created value chain. To achieve this, the activities performed by each organisation in each project, as well as their websites, were carefully analysed to gain a comprehensive understanding of their expertise. This process is essential for identifying key stakeholders who can make a significant contribution to the success of the project.

A total of 1381 participants were identified from the selected projects, some of whom participated in multiple projects. To determine their roles and expertise, we analysed each participant's involvement in the selected projects. This resulted in identifying around **560 potential stakeholders** who can be positioned in the value chain as potential stakeholders of the ReNEW project.

The potential stakeholders identified from the selected projects have been systematically summarised based on their organisational classification, country of origin, and expertise. This information has been strategically positioned within the various steps of the value chain. The details can be found in D5.1 Communication and Dissemination plan.

3.1.2 IWT-system Assessment

Inland waterway transport plays a vital role in our interconnected world, facilitating the movement of goods and people along waterways. However, to ensure its continued efficiency and effectiveness it must be able to constantly innovate. The first step in the process to formulate a capacity building strategy will be to assess the IWT system to clarify the context.

To begin with, the assessment delves into the structure of the system, as accurately as possible evaluating its strengths and weaknesses as a cohesive unit. It will answer the question of what makes IWT unique in comparison to other transport modes. Secondly, it identifies the nuanced differences within the IWT-system between different stakeholder categories and highlights the different dynamics within and between these groups. Central to this assessment are critical aspects such as organisational structure, governance frameworks, management systems, financial robustness, human resources, available infrastructure, policies and technical capabilities. The combination of these elements forms the IWT landscape, and understanding their impact and interactions is paramount to driving the sustainable innovation progress.

A key facet of the capacity assessment that should be highlighted is the assessment of the skills and knowledge of individuals within stakeholder groups, organisations and companies who could implement the newly studied innovations. This analysis illuminates the skills landscape, highlighting levels of proficiency and identifying potential areas for upskilling or training interventions. In addition, the assessment identifies specific competencies and expertise that are essential for the successful implementation of researched practices.

A variety of methods are used to gather the necessary insights, including surveys, interviews and skills assessments. These tools serve as a conduit to uncover existing skills and knowledge gaps, paving the way for targeted interventions and strategic improvements. This will be more extensively described in a further section.

In essence, assessing the capacity of the inland waterway system is a multifaceted endeavour that involves a holistic examination of its operational dynamics, the network of stakeholder and competency landscapes. By embarking on this journey of this system assessment, a context is clarified for the capacity building and policy recommendations.

3.1.3 Assessment of Adaptability Capabilities

Next step after clarifying the context is evaluating each part of this context on its impact on the ability to adopt innovations by the different stakeholder groups. The goal is to identify both tangible (e.g. infrastructural, financial...) and intangible (e.g. knowledge, governance...) gaps that can provide barriers to the adoption of innovations by different categories of stakeholders. Identifying these deficiencies specific to each stakeholder group will help to provide a specific strategy in capacity building later on.

The assessment also extends to evaluating the resilience and adaptability of the wider system. This includes examining how existing infrastructure, processes and regulations may affect the uptake or implementation of innovations. Factors such as compatibility with existing systems, regulatory compliance and organisational culture are taken into account to assess the system's readiness for change.

Ultimately, the knowledge gained from assessing adaptive capacity provides valuable guidance for all parts of the IWT-system. By understanding the strengths and weaknesses of the system in terms of resource availability, infrastructure and compatibility with new technologies, informed strategies can be developed to foster innovation and drive positive change.

3.1.4 Methodology and Approach for Capacity Assessment

Within the ReNEW project different methodologies are used to collect the information for the assessment described within the previous two sections. As the task connected to this deliverable and its second version is an overarching task of the project it will receive input from all work packages.

The first work package will give context and a theoretical framework about the IWT system. An example of this will be the listing of hazards and vulnerabilities within IWT. This will mainly be used for the IWT-system assessment on what makes the IWT system unique in comparison to other transport modes. Furthermore, it will also study what is needed to make the IWT system resilience and sustainable. A visual overview including all tasks part of WP1 can be found below (Figure 3-2).

Figure 3-2 Connection between WP1 tasks and T5.4 sub tasks/deliverables

The second and third work packages both will study innovations or digital infrastructure that are conducted for implementing certain solutions. This will also include best practices that are broader than the innovations that will be demonstrated during the living labs. What is studied within these work packages will serve as an input for surveys that will be conducted for the final version of this deliverable. These surveys will aim to test the applicability of certain technologies by several stakeholder groups which are mainly barge companies, ports, IWT infrastructure managers and IWT equipment manufacturers. This way certain barriers for the uptake of innovations will be mapped and the applicability of possible solutions will be surveyed. A visual overview including all tasks part of WP2 and 3 can be found below (Figure 3-3).

Figure 3-3: Connection between WP2 and 3 tasks and T5.4 sub tasks/deliverables

The fourth work package consists of the living labs within the ReNEW project. These living labs will generate learnings about how to implement certain innovations that will be demonstrated. This will give insights on which legal and technological barriers are present for the implementation of these certain innovations. Furthermore, these particular innovations also will be used as examples of innovations of which the applicability will be questioned by the surveys. A visual overview including all tasks part of WP4 can be found below (Figure 3-4).

Figure 3-4 Connection between WP4 tasks and T5.4 sub tasks/deliverables

The fifth work package is the outreach and upscale work package. First of all, this work package will consist of the stakeholder mapping which is already described within this deliverable and will also be further worked out in the second half of the ReNEW project. This stakeholder mapping will be important for the survey because it creates an eco-system of stakeholders that can be questioned. It will map the different stakeholder categories for which the surveys can be specifically tailored to analyse certain parts of the IWT-system. An additional part of the fifth work package is the exploitation and commercialisation strategy. This will give insights on the potential opportunities of certain innovations and the prerequisites for implementation. A visual overview of the internal connection of task 5.4 related to this deliverable and other tasks within the work package is given below (Figure 3-5).

Figure 3-5 the internal connection of task 5.4 related to this deliverable and other tasks within WP5

Additionally, to the surveys that will be sent, extra information will be added by organising workshops/symposiums and interviewing experts. Specifically for mapping the existing European or national policies within the IWT-sector an extra desk research will be conducted. Furthermore, collaborations with other EU projects or initiatives will be pursued within the same theme to exchange experience and knowledge. The combination of receiving input from different work packages and the methods of interacting with stakeholders will provide the needed information for the final system assessment. The collaboration with sister project and initiatives is part of Task 5.1 and will be further elaborated within deliverables linked to this task. In the table below a non exhaustive list of potential projects and initiatives is given.

Table 3-1 Non exhaustive list of potential projects and initiatives for collaboration.

Name project/Ininitiative	Description
Naideas III action programme	A list of actions to be undertaken by IWT in order to comply with Green Deal. IWT is in this context more to be seen as the regulators/ infrastructure managers rather than the industry itself. DG-MOVE considers this as an expert - group.
DINA	Expert group which focuses on digitalisation. Last summer's output was a document presenting IWT 's vision on digitalisation (from authorities perspective). Next step is to release a tender which should lead tot he implementation of the vision.
ETP - ALICE	The European Technology Platform for Logistics and supply management in Europe. ALICE is interesting because this platform works on greening and puts IWT in the supply chain perspective and not as a stand alone.
ETP – Waterborne	This association is driving the research agenda of the EU when it comes to the vessels (green, autonomous,..) . This ETP is at the drawingboard of Waterborne related project proposals; some in the context of the Waterborne partnership zero-emission waterborne transport (ZEWT) some outside of that.
PLATINA3	The EU-funded PLATINA3 project will provide targeted coordination and support activities to promote inland waterway transport (IWT) in Europe. Starting from January 2021, the project will run for 30 months. In this period the project will make the bridge towards future research, innovation and implementation needs within IWT in Europe. The main objective is to provide the knowledge base for the implementation of the EU Green Deal in view of further development of the European Commissions' IWT action programme (NAIADES) towards 2030. The platform will be a catalyst for awareness, stakeholder engagement and uptake of outcomes from related national and European projects and initiatives. PLATINA3 will consolidate their findings, assess their impacts and gaps.[12]
PLOTO	PLOTO aims at increasing the resilience of the Inland WaterWays (IWW) infrastructures and the connected land infrastructures, thus ensuring reliable network availability under unfavourable conditions, such as extreme weather, accidents and other kinds of hazards. [13]
CRISTAL	The key objective of the CRISTAL project is to increase the share of freight transport on inland water transport (IWT) by a minimum of 20% and to demonstrate on its three pilot sites (Italy, Poland and France) strategies to improve reliability by 80%. CRISTAL project will assure IWT capacity at 50% even during extreme weather events.[14]
Foremast	unded by the Horizon Europe programme, the 3-year long FOREMAST project will address the urgent need for sustainable transport solutions in urban and coastal areas, with the aim to create a paradigm shift towards cleaner and more efficient logistics. The "SFAZ" vessel, to be developed within the project, will allow the sustainable transport of goods along inland waterways, reducing road congestion, lowering emissions and improving overall accessibility.[15]

3.1.5 Timeline

This deliverable will act as a guide for the second half of the project to reach the final version of this deliverable. The different aspects discussed in previous chapters will be executed within three distinct phases (Figure 3-6).

- I. Phase one from M18 till M23:
By engaging with the different WP's an efficient way of funnelling useful information will be set up. This will also include compiling the useful information from the different deliverables for the final version of this deliverable. When the information of first half of the project is compiled it can be analysed which information is still missing. This will help to create the different surveys together with the rest of WP5 task leaders, which will be sent out from M24-25 on. This information will also be used for the planned symposia's in M24 and M28. Analysing the existing policies will also be part of this together with the collaboration of sister projects.
- II. Phase two from M24 till M31:
Send out surveys and organise two symposia. If extra information is needed interviews could be conducted with different stakeholders. As set up during the first phase information will be funnelled from the different work packages and analysed.
- III. Phase three from M32 till M36:
In this phase The final information will be analysed and brought together to the final version of this deliverable.

Figure 3-6: Timeline within second half of the project

3.2 Capacity Building and Policy Recommendations Strategy

The goal of the final version of this deliverable will be to formulate a capacity building strategy that takes into account the diversity of all stakeholders. Furthermore, a whitepaper will be drawn up that will include a roadmap and a set of key policy recommendations. This deliverable will describe the contents of this capacity building strategy and policy recommendations.

3.2.1 Capacity Building Strategy

Capacity building is a fundamental aspect of promoting sustainable development and ensuring the long-term impact of innovations. With clear goals and objectives, capacity building efforts aim to provide a strategy to gather the necessary skills, knowledge and resources to effectively implement and sustain innovative solutions which will take into account the differences between the different potential adopters. Capacity building strategies and approaches include a range of activities such as training, knowledge exchange, institutional support, resource mobilisation and technology development. An example of knowledge exchange will be the two symposiums that are planned at the end of the project.

Sustainability is a key consideration in capacity building efforts, with strategies aimed at ensuring that outcomes are sustained beyond the duration of the project. The aim is to share lessons learned, best practices and recommendations from the research and living labs within the project with the members of the IWT-sector. This includes documenting and disseminating successes, challenges and lessons learned from project's initiatives. By sharing knowledge and experiences, stakeholders and consortium members of the different living labs can learn from each other and refine their approaches to better meet evolving needs and circumstances.

In conclusion, capacity building is a dynamic and multifaceted process that is essential for realising the long-term impact of innovations. By setting clear goals, engaging stakeholders, identifying specific needs, implementing effective strategies, ensuring sustainability, and sharing lessons learned, capacity building efforts can drive meaningful change and contribute to sustainable development outcomes.

3.2.2 Policy Recommendations

The main goal will be to evaluate the project and some external selected good practices against the existing policies and propose any necessary additions or amendments to the European-wide policies. Hence it is required to list the existing policies and check that our proposed technologies have policy-related implementation barriers. The focus within the final versions of this deliverable will be the EU wide regulations and less the regional specific regulations.

The way to do this will be a combination between literature review, engaging with European policy-related associations like ALICE and engage with the LL partners or other relevant stakeholders. The living labs within the project will be particularly interesting because they will have experience with encountering legal barriers while demonstrating.

The final conclusions will be consolidated in a white paper consisting of a road map and policy recommendations that would help to overcome the shortcomings that were found within the existing policies. These recommendations aim to help minimising the legislative barriers for IWT-system's members to embark on the journey of implementing the project's innovations that will help for a more sustainable and resilient IWT-system.

4 Conclusion

The purpose of this document is to outline a roadmap for achieving the final version of the report by the project's conclusion. The ultimate objective is to develop a capacity building strategy tailored to the unique requirements of each stakeholder group involved in the IWT-system. This strategy is intended to provide guidance for implementing various innovations explored and demonstrated within the ReNEW project.

Specifically focusing on the legislative aspects of new technology implementation, a white paper will be produced, detailing a roadmap and offering policy recommendations.

This deliverable delineates the necessary information about the IWT-system essential for constructing a detailed context. It also specifies the tools to be utilized for collecting this information. Once this context is established, it becomes feasible to formulate a capacity building strategy and propose modifications or enhancements to existing policies.

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